

Highlights

Hierarchical control based on a hybrid nonlinear predictive strategy for a solar-powered absorption machine facility

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- Three models of the absorption chillers are validated
- Dwell-time and stress zone concepts are included in the control structure
- The lower layer PI controller enhances robustness of the hierarchical control system
- The hybrid control can control the entire plant smoothly regardless of mode switching

Hierarchical control based on a hybrid nonlinear predictive strategy for a solar-powered absorption machine facility

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Abstract

This work presents a hierarchical control framework to control a solar thermal facility aiming to provide the required operating conditions for an absorption chiller machine. The CIESOL thermal plant, located at the University of Almería (Spain), is proposed as a case study in which a solar collector field, two accumulation tanks, a gas heater, and its valve models are used in a trustworthy simulation environment. Herein, the thermal plant dynamic representation is completed by presenting the absorption chiller modeling, in which three distinct models, namely, a first principle lumped parameters, an AutoRegressive with eXogenous input (ARX), and a Nonlinear ARX (NARX) models, are validated. Accordingly, by using these models, the hierarchical control based on a hybrid nonlinear predictive controller is formulated, considering essential automatic control concepts to enhance robustness and performance. Dwell-time and stress zone are embedded in the operating condition constraints of the hybrid control component of the upper layer. In addition, a lower layer based on Proportional-Integral (PI) controllers is designed to overcome the valve's nonlinear dynamics and to improve dis-

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turbance rejection on the regulatory layer. The results demonstrate that the hierarchical structure controls the solar plant in a way that complies with the specifications, presenting a smooth behavior regardless of the mode switching and keeping the required conditions for the absorption chiller for more than 85% of the simulated time, both on sunny and cloudy days.

Keywords: Hybrid control, Hierarchical control, Solar energy, Absorption machine, Solar thermal plant efficiency

1. Introduction

Energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions have increased considerably in recent decades due to the substantial population growth, the modern society's quest for high living standards, and, hence, the industrial sector boom to meet such demands [1, 2, 3]. Likewise, it is also broadly established in the recent literature that the building sector accounts for approximately 40% of the global energy use and almost 33% of the greenhouse gas emissions worldwide [4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9]. Thus, the concerns about global warming and the imminent energy crisis alert appeal to any effort to enhance energy management in the building sector since it is evident that even small contributions can reduce large amounts of energy waste and greenhouse gas emissions.

One of the compelling manners to efficiently deal with the building sector energy consumption is to employ solar thermal power associated with Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) systems. The principle is to take advantage of renewable solar energy and use the sun's irradiance to heat a Heat Transfer Fluid (HTF), which is responsible for powering the building's HVAC systems, either for cooling or heating purposes [10]. In the case of cooling demands, an absorption chiller can interconnect the primary circuit of a solar thermal plant to the secondary circuit (HVAC components). Hence, an absorption closed-cycle in the absorption machine can reduce the temperature of the secondary fluid used for the building's cooling demands [11]. Indeed, the cooling demand is entirely in phase with the solar irradiance since the higher the solar irradiance, the higher the request for cooling indoor ambient.

The use of solar-powered absorption machines has been the focus of promising studies in the literature, mainly in what concerns modeling, control, and overall energy management [12, 13, 14, 15]. Correspondingly, it is

widely known that solar thermal plants are efficiently managed by employing advanced automatic control strategies [16, 17]. The control system is in charge of properly controlling the energy flow in the solar system either concerning economic or energy criteria, thus, avoiding energy waste and unnecessary use of non-renewable sources. The outstanding performance of control strategies is mainly related to their capabilities in addressing the highly nonlinear system dynamics, correctly rejecting meteorological disturbances, dealing with transport delays, and maintaining the operating conditions regardless of the different subsystems' activation, namely, tanks, gas heater, and valves [18, 19, 20, 21].

Concerning the activation/operation of solar thermal subsystems, this matter is widely treated in the control literature as a hybrid control problem, in which continuous and discrete variables dictate the system's behavior. The continuous variables are related to the process-related ones, such as temperatures, fluid flows, levels, and irradiance. On the other hand, the discrete variables are mainly associated with the activation/deactivation of the subsystems and valves, in which binary type-variables represent the subsystem status [22].

Regarding the hybrid control for solar-powered absorption chillers, crucial contributions have appeared in [23, 24, 25, 26, 27]. Moreover, recently in [28], the authors have proposed a nonlinear model predictive controller (NMPC) in which a multilayer control structure controls the system's operating modes, handling the discrete component, and the solar collector field outlet temperature, the continuous one. Nevertheless, it is important to highlight that, although essential issues have been addressed for the hybrid conditions of solar systems, the mentioned works have lacked control solutions that consider the system operation requirements in the control optimization problem, which have been addressed afterward in [29].

Therefore, in the light of the state of the art of hybrid controllers for solar-powered absorption chillers, this work presents a hierarchical control structure based on a hybrid nonlinear model predictive control for a solar thermal facility. The main goal is to propose an advanced control structure that can take full advantage of solar energy to keep the power requirements for the absorption chiller functioning while attending to the solar plant system operating conditions. Since the operating conditions define the subsystem configurations, the hierarchical controller must guarantee a stable and continuous operation of the absorption chiller regardless of the plant switching modes. The contributions presented herein derive from two bases:

- i First, an absorption machine modeling is performed, aiming to represent faithfully an existing facility, the CIESOL thermal plant, located at the University of Almería (Almería, southern east Spain). Three models are proposed, focusing on robustness and simple formulation that must be accounted for to develop predictive controllers. Thus, a simplified lumped-parameters first principle model and two data-driven models, namely, AutoRegressive with eXogenous input (ARX) and a Nonlinear ARX (NARX), are developed and validated in this work.
- ii Secondly, a hierarchical control structure is proposed, wherein the upper layer is in charge of providing optimal set-points for the regulatory lower layer controllers. The upper controller is formulated as a Hybrid Practical Nonlinear Model Predictive Control (HPNMPC), which accounts for the operating requirements of the plant, and, thus, the system’s mode changes along the prediction horizon. The regulatory lower layer is formulated using Proportional-Integral controllers with anti wind-up (PI-AW), responsible for controlling the water flow rates to achieve the required operating temperature of the absorption chiller.

The control structure is built upon the contributions presented in [29] by adding crucial control aspects to enhance the overall control algorithms: i) the PI-AW lower layer contributes to eliminating the nonlinearities in valves dynamics, thus, improving robustness and avoiding unmeasured disturbances effects in the water flow; ii) a slacked zone control optimization problem is employed to reduce the temperature threshold extrapolation and provide more degrees of freedom to the controller; iii) critical aspects regarding modes switching are investigated, mainly concerning dwell-timing [30, 31, 32], and stress zone [33, 34] tuning. Moreover, this work makes progress over the results presented in [28]. First, in [28], an NMPC controller is used only to control the solar collector’s outlet temperature, and, in the lower layer, fuzzy logic is used to determine the mode of operation. In contrast, herein, the HPNMPC controls the entire plant, manipulating all the available water flows in the systems and measuring all systems temperatures. Moreover, in [28], the authors employed mode switching constraints to obtain smooth shifting, while in this work, the operating conditions dictate which mode the system should operate, and the HPNMPC attends to it. Finally, the fuzzy logic can be much more complicated with the algorithm made up of several “if” conditions, whereas, herein, each operating condition is specified

separately, and a simple truth table solution combines the systems status to define the current operating mode.

It is worth mentioning that although the CIESOL solar thermal plant is used as a case study in this work, the proposed investigation can be extended to different solar plants with distinct subsystems as long as the principles for hybrid modeling and control designing are followed.

This work is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the CIESOL systems models, including the absorption machine modeling validation. In Section 3, the CIESOL operating conditions are established for the development of the control structure. In Section 4, the hierarchical control is designed. Section 5 presents the simulation results and then, in Section 6, the work's main conclusions are summarized.

2. CIESOL facility model

This section depicts the validated models of the CIESOL facility (Fig. 1) subsystems, including the novel proposed models for the absorption chiller. The solar collector field, tanks, gas heater, and fluid mix models are borrowed from [29], while the valve dynamics and the absorption chiller are detailed fully. The audience is referred to the Appendix A of [29] to consult the comprehensive descriptions of the model parameters.

Figure 2 presents the scheme of the CIESOL facility primary circuit operating in the summer mode, which is the focus of this work, wherein the absorption chiller interconnects the primary and secondary circuits (HVAC systems). This configuration is employed to guarantee the refrigeration of the CIESOL building rooms taking advantage of the solar collector field as the main energy source. Valves V1 and V4 are responsible for regulating $u_2(t)$ and $u_3(t)$, which are the water flow that goes to the solar collectors and the absorption machine. On the contrary, valves V2 and V3 only operate in on-off positions, which defines the tanks operating mode (load or unload).

2.1. Solar collector field

A validated lumped-parameters model [29] is employed as the solar collector field model, described by

Figure 1: CIESOL solar collector field - courtesy of CIESOL, University of Almería

Figure 2: CIESOL primary circuit scheme

$$\begin{aligned}
\rho_f \cdot C_f \cdot A_{sc} \cdot \frac{dT_{sc,o}(t)}{dt} &= \beta \cdot I(t - d_I) - \frac{H_{sc}}{L_{eq}} \cdot (\bar{T}_{sc}(t) - T_a(t)) \\
&\quad - \rho_f \cdot C_f \cdot SCS(t) \cdot \frac{u_2(t - d_{u_2})}{c_s} \cdot \frac{T_{sc,o}(t) - T_{sc,in}(t - d_{T,in})}{L_{eq}},
\end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

in which $T_{sc,o}(t)$ and $T_{sc,in}(t)$ are the outlet and inlet temperatures, respectively. The variable $\bar{T}_{sc}(t)$ denotes the mean temperature of the solar collectors calculated between $T_{sc,o}(t)$ and $T_{sc,in}(t)$. $I(t)$ is the solar irradiance, $T_a(t)$ the ambient temperature, $u_2(t)$ is the water flow, and d_I , d_{u_2} and $d_{T,in}$ are the transport delays associated with the respective variable. The binary variable is $SCS(t)$, that represents the activation status of this system.

2.2. Accumulation tanks

The validated accumulation tanks' model [29] is developed as stratified solution, representing faithfully the different sections temperature. Two tanks of 5000 l are modeled, considering three sections in each tank. The model equations are detailed as

$$\begin{aligned}
\rho_f \cdot C_f \cdot V_{t,a,s} \cdot \frac{dT_{t,a,s}(t)}{dt} &= \rho_f \cdot C_f \cdot u_1(t) \cdot TOS(t) \cdot T_{ft,a,s}(t) \\
&\quad + U_{t,a,s} \cdot SA_{t,a,s} (T_a(t) - T_{t,a,s}(t)) \\
&\quad + U_{t,a,s-1,s} \cdot A_{t,a,s-1,s} (T_{t,a,s-1}(t) - T_{t,a,s}(t)) \\
&\quad + U_{t,a,s,s+1} \cdot A_{t,a,s,s+1} (T_{t,a,s+1}(t) - T_{t,a,s}(t)),
\end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

in which $T_{ft,a,s}(t)$ is defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
T_{ft,a,s}(t) &= (T_{t,a,s-1}(t) - T_{t,a,s}(t)) \cdot m(t) \\
&\quad + (T_{t,a,s+1}(t) - T_{t,a,s}(t)) \cdot (1 - m(t)).
\end{aligned}$$

The subindices a and s represent the tank and its section, respectively. The modeled temperatures for the Tank 1 are $T_{t,1,1}$, $T_{t,1,2}$ and $T_{t,1,3}$, being the bottom, middle and top temperatures. Correspondingly, $T_{t,2,1}$, $T_{t,2,2}$ and $T_{t,2,3}$, represent the temperatures for the Tank 2. The variable $u_3(t)$ is the global water flow, provided by the pump to the primary circuit. The variable $TOS(t)$ is the binary variable that defines if the tank is active, and $m(t)$ represents the water flow direction, either loading or unloading the tanks.

2.3. Gas heater

The gas heater subsystem is employed to increase the temperature that enters the absorption machine if the solar collector field does not provide enough power. Evidently, its use must be avoided, but its modeling is crucial for the system's operation since the operating modes eventually account for the gas heater operation. The validated model equations are given by [29]

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_f \cdot C_f \cdot V_g \cdot \frac{dT_{gh}(t)}{dt} = & U_{ga} \cdot A_g \cdot (T_a(t) - T_g(t)) \\ & + GH(t) \cdot U_{gto} \cdot ((\log_{10}(9 \cdot \sqrt{Reg(t)}) + 1) \cdot T_{gh,gas}(t)) - T_{gh}(t) \\ & + \rho_f \cdot C_f \cdot u_3(t) \cdot (T_{gh,in}(t) - T_g(t)), \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

wherein $T_{gh}(t)$ and $T_{gh,in}(t)$ are the gas heater outlet and inlet temperatures, respectively. The variable $T_{gh,gas}(t)$ is the inside gas temperature, $Reg(t)$ is the gas flow regulation (0 - 100%), and $GH(t)$ is the binary variable related to the gas heater activation in the system.

2.4. Valve dynamic

In order to represent the effects of the lower control layer on hierarchical control for valves V1 and V4, the CIESOL valves dynamic is modeled. Actuators' dynamics are commonly modeled in practical scenarios to reduce their nonlinear influence and minimize unmeasured disturbance effects over the manipulated variable, requiring regulatory layer control. Thus, a model identification procedure is performed using actual data from the CIESOL facility, relating the water flow $u_2(t)$ and the valve opening, namely OP_{V1} . The standard identification procedure from the MATLAB Mathworks toolbox is employed due to its straightforward and trusting algorithm, which aims to minimize the Mean Square Error (MSE) of the model parameters and the real input/output data. In this case, the objective is to approximate the nonlinear valve behavior to a first-order model. Figure 3 details the model validation, and Eq. (4) the linear identified model

$$\tau_V \frac{du_2(t)}{dt} = K_V * OP_{V1}(t) - u_2(t), \quad (4)$$

in which $\tau_V = 25.54$ s is the time constant, $u_2(t)$ is the water flow, and $K_V = 0.0695$ m³/(h) is the model gain. The model calibration achieved a Mean Square Error (MSE) of 0.1727 m³/h, demonstrating a satisfactory

Figure 3: Valve V1 model identification

index performance. Notice that the identified gain tries to translate the main behavior since from Fig. 3 is notable that the gains are not the same throughout the test. This fact corroborated the need to apply a lower level regulatory control regarding the valve operation. Moreover, this model is provided for valve V1, but its dynamic is replicated in valve V4 as the valve manufacturer is the same.

The hydraulic distributions that occur in valves V1 and V4 are reconstituted in points P1 and P2 (see Fig. 3), respectively, in which P1 mixes the water flows that go towards the tanks, defining the solar collector field's final temperature, and P4 mixes the fluids that come after the absorption machine, and define the solar collector field's inlet temperature. In addition, the fluids mix in points P1 and P2 are modeled using static energy balances [29]. Therefore, this circumstance appeals for an adequate model of the absorption machine that can translate the evolution of its outlet temperatures since it affects the entire system's behavior.

2.5. Absorption chiller modeling

Several studies have been developed in recent years on the faithful representation of the absorption chiller sections: the generator, condenser, evaporator, and absorber, which culminated in complex and evolved models that relate the physical-chemical properties and energy balance throughout the

machine [15, 35, 36]. These studies require measurements of several variables and the knowledge of particular chemical properties that are not always available, mainly because commercial developers are very restrictive about their products.

Therefore, in this work, suitable models of absorption chillers are proposed regarding the fidelity/complexity trade-off for developing MPC strategies. Simplified solutions are offered to represent the dynamics of the CIESOL absorption machine, based on first principle equations and two data-driven models, ARX and NARX. The models are employed in the absorption machine's generator, evaporator, and condenser, which are related to the temperature dynamics in the primary and secondary circuit, and the refrigeration tower.

The object of study in this work is the Yazaki WFC SC 20 absorption chiller, depicted in Fig. 4, which technical data is described in Table 1.

Figure 4: CIESOL Yazaki absorption machine

For the first principle model, a lumped-parameters energy balance is proposed, inspired by the work in [28]. The following equations represent each

Table 1: CIESOL absorption chiller specifications

Item	Specification
Model	Yazaki WFC SC 20
Type	H ₂ O/LiBr
Electrical requirement	400 V, 50 Hz, 3ph.
Electrical power	260 W
Cooling capacity	70.3 kW
Chilled water inlet temp.	12 °C
Chilled water flow	11 m ³ /h
Evaporator pressure	65.8 kPa
Condenser heat rejection	170,8 kW
Cooling water inlet temp.	31 °C
Cooling water flow	36.7 m ³ /h
Heating inlet power	100 kW
Heating water inlet temp.	88 °C
Heating temperature limits	73 - 95 °C
Generator pressure	46.4 kPa
Heating water flow	17.3 m ³ /h

absorption chiller section:

Generator

$$C_g \cdot \frac{dT_{g,out}}{dt} = Q_{burner} - Q_{g,loss} - C_p \cdot \rho \cdot u_3(t) \cdot (T_{g,out} - T_{g,in}), \quad (5)$$

Evaporator

$$C_e \cdot \frac{dT_{e,out}}{dt} = -Q_{cool} + Q_{e,loss} + C_p \cdot \rho \cdot \dot{m}_e \cdot (T_{e,out} - T_{e,in}), \quad (6)$$

Condenser

$$C_c \cdot \frac{dT_{c,out}}{dt} = Q_{ref} - Q_{c,loss} + C_p \cdot \rho \cdot \dot{m}_c \cdot (T_{c,out} - T_{c,in}), \quad (7)$$

in which C_g , C_e and C_c are the heat capacity of the generator, evaporator, and condenser, respectively. Then, Q_{burner} , $Q_{g,loss}$, Q_{cool} , $Q_{e,loss}$, Q_{ref} , and $Q_{c,loss}$ are the lumped parameters used to identify the thermal power in each module of the absorption machine. The available measured variables used for calibrate the models are the outlets temperature $T_{g,out}$, $T_{e,out}$, and $T_{c,out}$,

inlet temperature, $T_{g,in}$, $T_{e,in}$, and $T_{c,in}$, and the water flows, $u_3(t)$, \dot{m}_e and \dot{m}_c .

Regarding the data-driven model, the ARX representation is detailed as

$$A(q^{-1}) \cdot y(t) = B(q^{-1}) \cdot u(t) + e(t), \quad (8)$$

in which $y(t)$ is the system output, $u(t)$ is the system input and $e(t)$ the model error. In addition, the polynomials $A(q^{-1})$ and $B(q^{-1})$ are parameterized as

$$\begin{aligned} A(q^{-1}) &= 1 + a_1 \cdot q^{-1} + \dots + a_{na} \cdot q^{-na} \\ B(q^{-1}) &= b_1 \cdot q^{-1} + \dots + b_{nb} \cdot q^{-nb}, \end{aligned}$$

wherein q^{-1} is the backward shift operator, a_1, \dots, a_{na} are the output polynomial coefficients, b_1, \dots, b_{nb} are the input polynomial coefficients, and na and nb are the polynomial orders.

The absorption chiller's functioning can be very complex and nonlinear. Therefore, the previously proposed ARX model can be enhanced to establish a more realistic representation of the nonlinear absorption chiller evolution by including a nonlinear function on the time-series autoregression, culminating in a NARX modeling. The new NARX model has been successfully employed in different varieties of systems [37, 38] due to its diversity of nonlinear representations, which can be based, for instance, on neural networks, polynomials, wavelet, and sigmoid network functions. The general NARX model can be represented as a series-parallel form, as

$$\hat{y}(t+1) = f(y(t), y(t-1), \dots, y(t-n_y), u(t), u(t-1), \dots, u(t-n_u)) \quad , \quad (9)$$

in which the function $f(\cdot)$ is the nonlinear function relating the inputs and outputs regressors. The NARX variables structure is detailed in the block diagram in Fig 5. As can be noted, to calculate the predicted output $\hat{y}(t+1)$, not only the linear regressors polynomials are taking into account, as in the ARX algorithm, but also a nonlinear function $f(\cdot)$ can relate the past inputs and outputs to improve the prediction performance when nonlinear relations exist among the data. In addition, a static offset is applied to the combined outputs of the linear and nonlinear blocks aiming to remove the stationary error.

2.5.1. Models calibration

First, an initial data processing step is required to select the actual data on which the system is operating correctly and filter input and output noise

Figure 5: NARX variables structure block diagram

from sensor measurements. Seven days of CIESOL operation are used as calibrating data, in which the models' specifications are tuned in order to find the best compromise between simple order and good fit results through optimization methods. For all three approaches, the main goal is to minimize the mean square error, as follows:

$$\min J,$$

$$J = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^{i=N} \left((\hat{T}_{g,out}(i) - T_{g,out}(i))^2 + (\hat{T}_{v,out}(i) - T_{v,out}(i))^2 + (\hat{T}_{c,out}(i) - T_{c,out}(i))^2 \right), \quad (10)$$

in which the notation $\hat{x}(i)$ is the model output at sample i and $N=2320$ is the amount of calibration data, for a sampling time of 1 min. After several experiments, the models' set-up is achieved as follows:

- First principle lumped-parameters model:
 - Optimization method based on Genetic Algorithm is used to find the model parameters
 - Input data: $T_{g,in}(t)$, $T_{e,in}(t)$, $T_{c,in}(t)$, $u_3(t)$, $\dot{m}_e(t)$ and $\dot{m}_c(t)$
 - Decision variables: C_g , C_e , C_c , Q_{burner} , $Q_{g,loss}$, Q_{cool} , $Q_{e,loss}$, Q_{ref} , and $Q_{c,loss}$
- ARX model

- Input data: $T_{g,in}(t)$, $T_{e,in}(t)$, $T_{c,in}(t)$, $u_3(t)$, $\dot{m}_e(t)$ and $\dot{m}_c(t)$
 - Generator model order: $na = 2$, $nb = 2$. No delays
 - Evaporator model order: $na = 2$, $nb = 2$. No delays
 - Evaporator model order: $na = 4$, $nb = 2$. No delays
- NARX model
 - Input data: $T_{g,in}(t)$, $T_{e,in}(t)$, $T_{c,in}(t)$, $u_3(t)$, $\dot{m}_e(t)$ and $\dot{m}_c(t)$
 - Generator model order: $n_y = 3$, $n_u = 2$. No delays. Nonlinear function $f(\cdot)$ in Eq. (9) = Wavelet
 - Evaporator model order: $n_y = 2$, $n_u = 2$. No delays. Nonlinear function $f(\cdot)$ in Eq. (9) = Wavelet
 - Evaporator model order: $n_y = 2$, $n_u = 2$. No delays. Nonlinear function $f(\cdot)$ in Eq. (9) = Wavelet

For the ARX and NARX models, polynomial orders and the nonlinear function are chosen from repetitive trials, choosing the simplest models that have a low cost of Eq. (10), following the Akaike's criterion to achieve the trade-off between performance index and complexity. In addition, no delays were included since the analysis of the experimental data has shown an almost instant effect of the input and output variables.

2.5.2. Model validation

Three different days of the CIESOL absorption chiller operation are chosen for the calibration stage. Figures 6 - 8 depict the validation results of one-day operation of the three sections of the absorption machine, comparing the proposed models' results. Moreover, Table 2 details the performance indices regarding data-model fitness, namely, MSE, Root MSE (RMSE), normalized RMSE (nRMSE), mean error (\bar{E}), and percentage of error (E%). Also, computational cost is measured by computing the processing time of the entire operation t_{proc} , and the average mean time for each operation t_{mean} .

By analyzing the validation results, it can be noticed that the three strategies adequately describe the system dynamics, despite an offset error caused by the different operating conditions of the plant. However, considering the development of model-based controllers, the results point out that the first principle model achieves the best compromise between representativeness and computational cost, presenting acceptable fitness indices for the output error

Table 2: Performance comparison for the first principle (FP), ARX and NARX models. The highlighted indices are the smaller, and, hence, the best indices among the three compared models for each absorption machine section.

	Generator			Evaporator			Condenser		
	FP	ARX	NARX	FP	ARX	NARX	FP	ARX	NARX
MSE [$(^{\circ}\text{C})^2$]	1.247	1.217	0.816	1.170	0.524	0.377	1.258	0.409	0.376
RMSE [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	1.107	1.044	0.898	1.001	0.704	0.612	1.109	0.610	0.581
nRMSE [-]	0.016	0.015	0.013	0.119	0.084	0.072	0.035	0.019	0.018
\bar{E} [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	0.902	0.896	0.765	0.810	0.559	0.500	0.874	0.538	0.502
E% [%]	1.317	1.288	1.117	9.513	6.600	5.931	2.785	1.697	1.580
t_{proc} [s]	0.152	7.803	15.331	0.154	7.816	15.364	0.157	7.967	15.266
t_{mean} [ms]	0.2178	11.1791	21.9642	0.2206	11.1977	22.0115	0.2249	11.4140	21.8711

and considerably shorter computational processing time. Although an offset error caused by the different operating conditions of the plant is presented in the validated models, this issue can be easily overcome by implementing control strategies with an integral effect. Therefore, the lumped-parameters model is chosen for implementing the hierarchical controller investigated in this work.

3. CIESOL facility operating conditions

As evidenced in Section 2, the CIESOL facility can be operated in several manners, considering the activation of its different subsystems. In this section, the CIESOL plant configurations are detailed, considering the manipulation of each subsystem binary variable. Moreover, the operating conditions that define each plant configuration are presented, following the HPNMPC formulation [29].

3.1. CIESOL facility operation

The hierarchical control's primary objective is to guarantee maximum use of solar energy to power the absorption chiller entry requirements regardless of the subsystem operating mode changes while attending to the entire plant

Figure 6: Validation results for the generator section of the absorption machine for the first principle, ARX and NARX models.

Figure 7: Validation results for the evaporator section of the absorption machine for the first principle, ARX and NARX models.

Figure 8: Validation results for the condenser section of the absorption machine of the first principle, ARX and NARX models.

operating conditions. Based on this goal, the operating modes defined for the CIESOL facility must necessarily account for the solar collector field and the absorption machine. In addition, as observed from the subsystems models,

the binary variables define how the plant is set up. Thus, the discrete-binary variables treated in this work are: $SCS(t)$, $TOS1(t)$, $TOS2(t)$, $m(t)$ and $GH(t)$, Notice that $Reg(t) \in \mathbb{R} [0, 1]$ does not change the system's configuration, and thus is chosen as constant.

The CIESOL operating models are detailed as follows:

- Mode 1 - Solar Collector field: In this mode, only the solar collector field powers the absorption machine, in which the water flow mix in P1 is the final stage that defines the amount of energy that feeds the absorption machine generator.
- Mode 2 - Tanks unload: Here, the hot water stored in the tanks feeds up the absorption machine. In this configuration, the hot water coming from the solar collectors enter the hottest section of the tanks.
- Mode 3 - Tanks load: When the solar collector outlet temperature is higher enough, this thermal energy is stored in the tanks. Similar to Mode 2, the tanks power the absorption machine but now considering its coldest section.
- Mode 4 - Solar collectors and Gas Heater: In this mode, in the case that only the solar collectors are operating and the water temperature does not achieve the absorption machine operating conditions, the gas heater is turned on.
- Mode 5 - Tanks unload and Gas Heater: Correspondingly, in the case that the Mode 2 configuration does not achieve the necessary temperature, the gas heater is activated.
- Mode 6 - Similarly, if in Mode 3 the water temperature that goes to the absorption chiller is low, the gas heater is activated.

Following [29] for the HPNMPC control formulation, a binary variable $\delta \in \{0, 1\}$ is employed for each operating mode. Table 3¹ depicts the plant modes and the corresponding binary model variables.

By considering the presented definition, the actual system operation is set up mainly regarding $TOS1(t)$, $TOS2(t)$, and $m(t)$ variables, which are

¹The notation X represents the logical irrelevance of the variable to the binary mode output, which can be 1 or 0.

Table 3: CIESOL solar plant operating modes definition.

Mode	$SCS(t)$	$TOS1(t)$	$TOS2(t)$	$m(t)$	$GH(t)$
δ_1 : Mode 1	1	0	0	X	0
δ_2 : Mode 2	1	1	1	0	0
δ_3 : Mode 3	1	1	1	1	1
δ_4 : Mode 4	1	0	0	X	0
δ_5 : Mode 5	1	1	1	0	0
δ_6 : Mode 6	1	1	1	1	1

in charge of manipulating valves V2 and V3 (on/off). Hence, $GH(t)$ only defines the start-up of the gas heater, and it does not change the system configuration. On the other hand, the water flows $u_1(t)$, $u_2(t)$, and $u_3(t)$ are manipulated by the regulatory control layer over the valves V1 and V4 opening. Therefore, this framework defines the continuous and discrete control of the CIESOL facility.

3.2. CIESOL operating conditions

The operating conditions of the CIESOL plant define which mode must be set up to achieve a specific objective. These objectives are defined by design based on engineering projects and operators' insights. They are the essence of a smooth and continued operation of the facility since the harmony between the subsystems is mainly defined by each system's temperature profile that must keep the required conditions for the absorption chiller operation. Therefore, based on [29], specific conditions are imposed to relate the systems' profile temperature to a specific operation mode, as follows:

- 1 When $T_{t,2,3}(t)$ is higher than the temperature in P1, T_{P1} , then unload the tanks;
- 2 When T_{P1} is higher than the $T_{t,1,1}(t)$, then load the tank;
- 3 When $T_{gh,in}(t)$ is lower than the absorption machine reference temperature, then activate the gas heater.
- 4 When $T_{gh,o}(t)$ is higher than the absorption machine reference temperature, then deactivate the gas heater.

The presented conditions are designated to improve the plant performance considering maximizing the operating time and using the gas heater only when necessary. Nevertheless, specific issues must be handled regarding control design to guarantee smooth operation and avoid instability and chattering. Therefore, two theoretical control features, dwell-time and stress zone, are presented to improve system stability when mode switching occurs in hybrid systems. First, the dwell-timing concept is presented in [30], in which the main principle is to define a continuous-time variable called a timing signal t_{ep} that can take values in the closed interval $[0, \tau_{dw}]$ where τ_{dw} is a pre-specified positive constant called a dwell-time. When a so-called “event” occurs in the plant, t_{ep} is reset, according to a reset integrator rule $t_{ep} = 1$. In particular, for the proposed CIESOL thermal plant control objectives, the elapsed time τ_{dw} defines the necessary time to allow an operating mode switch. This operating condition is essential to avoid chattering due to mode changes, which forces the system to stay in the current plant configuration for a pre-defined tuning time τ_{dw} . This control feature can be translated into operating conditions as follows:

- 5 When t_{ep} is equal or greater than τ_{dw} then allow mode changes.

Furthermore, as discussed in [34], the strict operating condition that imposes the plant modes is a critical issue regarding the stability during the mode changes. This issue is evidenced especially in gain scheduling control approaches for nonlinear systems. For instance, the operating conditions defined previously are defined by real variables $T(t) \in \mathbb{R}$. Hence, infinitesimal variations even provoked by uncertainty components, such as sensor noise, can alter the plant’s operating conditions. Therefore, a stress zone is imposed to guarantee a broader zone in which the operating conditions are not modified. Specifically, the solution is managed in two folds: i) first consider the moving average value of the pre-defined variables used in the operating conditions; ii) add a constant stress variable ΔT to regulate the stress zone.

Therefore, the presented control aspects regarding each of the operating conditions can be translated mathematically as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
[\delta_{T_1} = 1] \leftrightarrow J_1(t) &= \Delta T_1 - (\overline{T}_{t,2,3}(t) - \overline{T}_{P1}(t)) \\
[\delta_{T_2} = 1] \leftrightarrow J_2(t) &= \Delta T_2 - (\overline{T}_{P1}(t) - \overline{T}_{t,1,1}(t)) \\
[\delta_{GH_1} = 1] \leftrightarrow J_3(t) &= \Delta T_3 - (T_{gh,in}(t) - T_{ref}(t)) \\
[\delta_{GH_2} = 1] \leftrightarrow J_4(t) &= \Delta T_4 - (T_{ref}(t) - T_g(t)) \\
[\delta_t = 1] \leftrightarrow J_5(t) &= t_{ep} - \tau_{dw} \\
[\delta_{GH} = 1] &= \widetilde{\delta_{GH_1}} \text{ AND } \delta_{GH_2}
\end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

in which the notation \overline{T} is the moving average of the corresponding variable and $\widetilde{\delta}$ the logical operation “NOT”. T_{ref} is the absorption machine temperature reference, J_i , $i \in \mathbb{I}[1, 5]$, and δ are the binary variables related to each operating condition. Notice that for each condition, there is an exclusive binary variable associated. For instance, when the condition J_1 is positive, then $\delta_1 = 1$, otherwise, $\delta_1 = 0$, and so on for all conditions. Finally, a truth table (see Table 4) is defined to relate the combination of the operating condition to the CIESOL plant configuration (the reader is referred to [29] for a comprehensive review of the discrete mode definition). Therefore, based on the presented discrete variables definition, the operating modes are suitable to be treated by the HPNMPC controller, and, hence, the hierarchical control framework can be formulated.

Table 4: Truth table for the discrete variables and operating modes, in which $\delta_{m_{k-1}}$ is the last operating mode. *The notation X represents the logical irrelevance of the variable to the binary mode output, which can be 1 or 0. The operator \wedge represent the logical operation “AND”.

Operating mode	δ_{T_1}	δ_{T_2}	δ_{GH}	δ_t	Output
δ_1	0	0	0	1	$= \widetilde{\delta_{T_1}} \wedge \widetilde{\delta_{T_2}} \wedge \widetilde{\delta_{GH}} \wedge \delta_t$
δ_2	1	0	0	1	$= \delta_{T_1} \wedge \widetilde{\delta_{T_2}} \wedge \widetilde{\delta_{GH}} \wedge \delta_t$
δ_3	0	1	0	1	$= \widetilde{\delta_{T_1}} \wedge \delta_{T_2} \wedge \widetilde{\delta_{GH}} \wedge \delta_t$
δ_3	1	1	0	1	$= \delta_{T_1} \wedge \delta_{T_2} \wedge \widetilde{\delta_{GH}} \wedge \delta_t$
δ_4	0	0	1	1	$= \widetilde{\delta_{T_1}} \wedge \widetilde{\delta_{T_2}} \wedge \delta_{GH} \wedge \delta_t$
δ_5	1	0	1	1	$= \delta_{T_1} \wedge \widetilde{\delta_{T_2}} \wedge \delta_{GH} \wedge \delta_t$
δ_6	0	1	1	1	$= \widetilde{\delta_{T_1}} \wedge \delta_{T_2} \wedge \delta_{GH} \wedge \delta_t$
δ_6	1	1	1	1	$= \delta_{T_1} \wedge \delta_{T_2} \wedge \delta_{GH} \wedge \delta_t$
$\delta_{m_{k-1}}$	X	X	X	0	$= \widetilde{\delta_t}$

4. Hierarchical HPNMPC

From the presented hybrid modeling, operating conditions, and binary variables declaration, in this section, the hierarchical control structure is formulated. The objective is to control the entire solar thermal plant aiming to achieve the required water inlet temperature of the absorption chiller generator by manipulating the continuous water flows $u_1(t)$, $u_2(t)$, and $u_3(t)$, in addition to the binary variables that define the plant configuration. Preliminary conditions are established a priori. First, it is assumed that $u_1(t)$ is controlled directly by the pump, in which an internal frequency inverter is embedded, as it occurs in the existing system. Hence, the lower layer control actuates only in V1 and V4 to control $u_2(t)$, and $u_3(t)$. Secondly, since this work is focused on achieving the operating requirements of the absorption machine, only the primary circuit is boarded, and stationary assumptions are imposed for the refrigeration tower and HVAC systems, which correspond to the condenser and evaporator sections of the absorption machine, respectively. Figure 9 depicts the control architecture structure, in which T_{ref} is the inlet temperature reference of the absorption chiller, Ref_{lim} is the zone control limits, formulated subsequently in the HPNMPC controller, and $u_{1_{opt}}(t)$, $u_{2_{opt}}(t)$, and $u_{3_{opt}}(t)$, are the optimal water flow values provided by the upper layer hybrid controller. The lower layer regulatory control provides as outputs the valve opening for V1 and V4 as OP_{V1} and OP_{V4} . The design of each control layer is given in sequence.

4.1. Upper layer - HPNMPC

The work in [29] inspires the upper layer controller formulation. A Hybrid PNMPC is presented in which the operating conditions are respected as a result of discrete variables combination. The PNMPC is a practical predictive control algorithm that uses the nonlinear models to formulated a linearized equation concerning the inputs and disturbances (see [39] for a the algorithm complete description). First, the PNMPC is extended to a hybrid formulation so that the predicted outputs in each operating mode are defined by

$$\hat{\mathbf{Y}} = \mathbf{F}_{m_{k-1}} + \mathbf{G}_M \cdot \Delta \mathbf{Z} + \mathbf{G}_{M_d} \cdot \Delta \mathbf{d} \quad (12)$$

in which $\hat{\mathbf{Y}}$ is a vector of all predicted temperatures using the models described in Section 2, $\Delta \mathbf{d} = [\Delta I(t), \Delta T_a(t)]$ are the estimated disturbances variations. $\mathbf{F}_{m_{k-1}}$ is the system free response calculated using the last inputs

Figure 9: Hierarchical control scheme based on a hybrid controller.

and outputs for the current plant mode m_{k-1} . The outputs treated in the prediction equation are:

$$\hat{\mathbf{Y}} = \left[\hat{T}_{sc,o}, \hat{T}_{P1}, \hat{T}_{t,1,1}, \hat{T}_{t,1,2}, \hat{T}_{t,1,3}, \hat{T}_{t,2,1}, \hat{T}_{t,2,2}, \hat{T}_{t,2,3}, \right. \\ \left. \hat{T}_{gh,o}, \hat{T}_{g,in}, \hat{T}_{g,out}, \hat{T}_{c,out}, \hat{T}_{e,out}, \hat{T}_{P2} \right]^T.$$

Moreover, \mathbf{G}_M and \mathbf{G}_{M_d} are the forced response matrices for each operating mode. In other words, these matrices are calculated as a concatenation of each \mathbf{G}_m and $\mathbf{G}_{m_d} \forall m \in [1, 6]$, that is

$$\mathbf{G}_M = [\mathbf{G}_1, \mathbf{G}_2, \dots, \mathbf{G}_{n_m}], \\ \mathbf{G}_{M_d} = [\mathbf{G}_{d_2}, \mathbf{G}_{d_3}, \dots, \mathbf{G}_{d_{n_m}}],$$

in which \mathbf{G}_m and \mathbf{G}_{m_d} are calculated as the gradient of the predicted outputs relative to the control increments and the disturbance increments for each operating mode m . The gradient is calculated at each sample time applying small increments in $\Delta \mathbf{u}$ and $\Delta \mathbf{d}$ using the nonlinear models to predict the

outputs along the horizon, which leads to the following construction of each matrix, respectively,

$$\mathbf{G}_M = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(t+1|t)}{\partial \Delta u(t|t)} & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(t+1|t)}{\partial \Delta u(t|t)} & \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(t+2|t)}{\partial \Delta u(t+1|t)} & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \cdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(t+N_p|t)}{\partial \Delta u(t|t)} & \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(t+N_p|t)}{\partial \Delta u(t+1|t)} & \cdots & \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(t+N_p|t)}{\partial \Delta u(t+N_c-1|t)} \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\mathbf{G}_{M_d} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(t+1|t)}{\partial \Delta d(t|t)} & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(t+1|t)}{\partial \Delta d(t|t)} & \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(t+2|t)}{\partial \Delta d(t+1|t)} & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \cdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(t+N_p|t)}{\partial \Delta d(t|t)} & \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(t+N_p|t)}{\partial \Delta d(t+1|t)} & \cdots & \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(t+N_p|t)}{\partial \Delta d(t+N_p-1|t)} \end{bmatrix}.$$

As a result, the form presented in Eq. (12) establishes a linear relation of the outputs related to the inputs and disturbances in the different plant configuration.

The control inputs, that is $\Delta \mathbf{u}_1$, $\Delta \mathbf{u}_2$ and $\Delta \mathbf{u}_3$, are associated to each operating model by employing a variable transformation, as follows

$$\Delta \mathbf{z}_m = \delta_m \cdot \Delta \mathbf{U}, \quad (13)$$

considering

$$\Delta \mathbf{Z} = [\Delta \mathbf{z}_1, \Delta \mathbf{z}_2, \cdots, \Delta \mathbf{z}_{n_m}]^\top, \quad (14)$$

in which $\Delta \mathbf{U} = [\Delta \mathbf{u}_1, \Delta \mathbf{u}_2, \Delta \mathbf{u}_3]$, $\Delta u(k) = u(k) - u(k-1)$ the inputs increments in discrete time, and n_m the number of operating modes. Hence, the operating modes can be associated exclusively with each set of the three inputs. For instance, if $\delta_1 = 1$, then $\Delta \mathbf{z}_1 = \Delta \mathbf{U}$, and the remaining $\Delta \mathbf{z}_2 \cdots \Delta \mathbf{z}_{n_m}$ will be zero since there is only one plant configuration at a time, as defined in Table 4. Therefore, the optimal calculated inputs will be only related to the operating mode $m = 1$.

Based on this assumption, the upper layer optimization problem can be

formalized as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{\Delta \mathbf{z}, y_{ref}, \Delta s} J_{HC}, \\ J_{HC} = & \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N_p} |T_{g,in}(k+i) - y_{ref}(k+i)|_{\mathbf{Q}}^2 + \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} |\Delta \mathbf{z}(k+i-1)|_{\mathbf{R}}^2 + |\Delta s|_{\mathbf{S}}^2 \right), \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

subjected to:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Process model equations, see Section 2,} \\ & \text{Operating constraints, see Section 3,} \\ & u_{min} \leq u_1(k+i-1) \leq u_{max}, \\ & u_{min} \leq u_2(k+i-1) \leq u_1(k+i-1), \\ & u_{min} \leq u_3(k+i-1) \leq u_1(k+i-1), \\ & \Delta \mathbf{U}_{min} \leq \Delta \mathbf{U} \leq \Delta \mathbf{U}_{max}, \\ & T_{sc_{min}} \leq T_{sc,o}(k+i) \leq T_{sc_{max}}, \\ & T_{ref} - Ref_{lim} \leq y_{ref}(k+i) \leq T_{ref} + Ref_{lim} \\ & y_{ref}(k+i) = T_{ref} + \Delta s, \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

wherein \mathbf{Q} , \mathbf{R} , and \mathbf{S} are the weighting factors for the outputs, inputs and the slack variable Δs . N_c and N_p are the control and prediction horizons, respectively, u_{min} and u_{max} are the limits of the water flow, and y_{ref} is an auxiliary variable used in the slacked zone control formulation. $T_{sc_{min}}$ and $T_{sc_{max}}$ are the solar collector field temperature constraints, and $\Delta \mathbf{U}_{min}$ and $\Delta \mathbf{U}_{max}$ are the water flow variations limits.

The purpose of this optimization problem is to use the hybrid models and the operational conditions to solve a Mixed-Integer Quadratic Programming (MIQP) (see [29] for the MIQP detailed formulation). Hence, using the hybrid model and operating conditions as constraints, the solution of Eq. (15) is the optimal water flows and the binary variable that relates to operating conditions to the plant configuration. In addition, the slacked zone control is proposed to keep the controlled temperature at the middle of the reference zone as much as possible, minimizing the use of the slack variable δs . This goal is achieved by choosing significantly high values for \mathbf{S} compared to \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{R} .

4.2. Lower layer - PI-AW

Regarding the lower layer control, a PI-AW strategy is proposed in order to guarantee a robust and steadier behavior of the manipulated variables. Although the concepts of classical PI-AW controllers are widely known, this control structure is very appealing for the purposes of this work. The lower layer can mitigate the valves' nonlinear behavior by adequately controlling the water flow, which is advantageous to the HPNMPC as it can assume that the desired water flow will be achieved, thus reducing the dynamic complexity of the predictive models. In addition, this lower layer can rapidly minimize the effects of unmeasured disturbances that affect the water flows, which is valuable for the temperature control of the entire plant.

The PI controller block presented in Fig. 9 is formulated considering the ideal form, in which its representation in the frequency-domain (s) is defined as follows:

$$C(s) = K_p \cdot \left(1 + \frac{1}{T_i \cdot s} \right) \quad (17)$$

in which K_p is the proportional gain and T_i is the integral time. In addition, an anti wind-up solution, based on the back-calculation scheme, is proposed to overcome the integral computation issues due to the actuator limits. Notice that two PI-AW controllers are imposed, in which their references are the optimal values calculated by the HPNMPC controllers, namely, $u_{2_{opt}}(t)$, and $u_{3_{opt}}(t)$. As a result, the PI-AW controllers provide the valve opening values $OP_{V1}(t)$ and $OP_{V4}(t)$.

The objective of implementing the PI-AW controller is to circumvent the nonlinear gain of valves V1 and V4, as presented in Section 2. Since the valve nonlinearity is given statically, it can be properly compensated due to the high speed of the PI-AW controller in closed-loop when applied in the actual system, which is sufficient from the point of view of the hierarchical control strategy proposed in this work.

Finally, after designing the control architecture and its components, the presented hierarchical controller is tested in a simulated scenario considering the CIESOL thermal plant facility.

5. Results

In this section, a rigorous simulation scenario is proposed to evaluate the performance of the hierarchical hybrid controller. The control structure

presented in Section 4 is employed to control the nonlinear hybrid systems presented in Section 2. Furthermore, actual data from the CIESOL facility is used to simulate the system demand and the meteorological conditions. Two scenarios are tested, considering a sunny day, with collected data from May 13, 2021, and a cloudy day from the dataset of May 14, 2021.

First, the HPNMPC and PI-AW control tuning are performed considering the smooth behaviour of the manipulated variables. The HPNMPC prediction horizon and sample time are tuned considering the system dynamics analysis presented in [40], in which the time constant and gain variations of the solar collector field linear model are studied. Moreover, the PI tuning follows the IMC method since no delay time is presented in the valve dynamics, and, thus, the control performance can present a robust and fast response regarding reference tracking [41]. Table 5 depicts the control tuning parameters for the HPNMPC considering, in addition, the dwell-time and the stress zone parameters. The adjustments were achieved after trial and error simulations considering the CIESOL plant practical specifications, stability and smooth performance. Also, $T_{s_{HC}} = 10$ s is the HPNMPC sampling time, and the moving average window for each variable specified in Section 3 is chosen as 1 min.

Furthermore, for the sake of demonstrating the effectiveness of the control structure without saturating the input limits and losing a degree of freedom, the water flow limits are altered, considering now that the maximum water flow limit is 20 m³/h. Therefore, the gain calculated in the valve dynamic is also changed to accommodate this modification, assuming now $K_v = 0.2$. Hence, in the simulated scenarios, the water flow can range from 0 - 20 m³/h for the valve opening of 0 - 100 %. Correspondingly, the SIMC tuning rule [41] is employed for the PI-AW parameters, resulting in the following adjustment for a control sample time $T_{s_{PI}} = 1$ s:

$$K_p = T_i / (0.2 \cdot (\lambda)) , T_i = 25.54 , \lambda = 0.8 \cdot 25.54 , T_{aw} = \sqrt{T_i}, \quad (18)$$

in which T_{aw} is the anti wind-up resetting parameter [16, 42].

It is important to note that a comparison of the proposed hybrid algorithm with respect to a non-hybrid solution has already been successfully performed in previous works. For more details, see [29].

Table 5: Control tuning parameters for the simulated Scenarios 1 and 2.

Control Parameters	Values
N_p [-]	80
N_c [-]	20
\mathbf{Q} [-]	[20, 20, 50]
R [-]	100
ΔU_{max} [m ³ /h]	[3, 2, 2]
ΔU_{min} [m ³ /h]	[-3, -2, -2]
u_{max} [m ³ /h]	20
u_{min} [m ³ /h]	3
$T_{sc,o_{max}}$ [°C]	95
$T_{sc,o_{min}}$ [°C]	25
Ref_{lim} [°C]	2.5
ΔT_1 [°C]	1
ΔT_2 [°C]	1
ΔT_3 [°C]	1.5
ΔT_4 [°C]	1
t_{dw} [-]	$90 \cdot T_s$

5.1. Scenario 1 - Sunny day

In this first scenario, a clear-sky irradiance profile is used to simulate the hierarchical controller. The controller operates only during the main period of the day, from 10 h to 15 h, when there is enough thermal power to be provided by the solar collector fields. In addition, the tanks' temperature starts the day at 80 °C, the gas heater regulator $REG(t)$ is set at 70%, and the solar collector field delays are chosen as $d_I = 53$ s, $d_{u_2} = 52$ s and $d_{T,in} = 57$ s, as observed from experimental data. Here, the estimated disturbance predictions for $I(t)$ and $T_a(t)$ are assumed constant as their effect on the overall hybrid control performance is barely observed.

Figure 10 depicts the critical variables controlled by the hierarchical controller throughout the plant, focusing on keeping the generator inlet temperature of the absorption chiller at the desired operating limits. Moreover, three distinct reference changes are proposed to observe the control behavior throughout the test.

As can be seen, the controlled variable $T_{g,in}(t)$ is kept most of the time in the middle of the reference zone, following the expected outcomes based on the formulation of the HPNMPC. Furthermore, it can also be noted

to capture the maximum amount of energy from the solar collector field by keeping $u_2(t)$ low and controlling the fluid mix in point P1, as long as the solar collector’s field temperature is within the operating threshold. Thus, the HPNMPC modulates the pump total flow $u_1(t)$ to distribute the thermal power throughout the plant while keeping the particular flows $u_2(t)$ and $u_3(t)$ to achieve the desired temperature to power the absorption chiller.

Regarding the lower layer control, Fig 11 details the PI-AW performance for controlling $u_2(t)$ and $u_3(t)$. As observed, the PI-AW tuning is well designed, and the lower layer control has no struggles in achieving the optimal water flows calculated by the HPNMPC.

Figure 11: PI-AW performance for the sunny day scenario.

5.2. Scenario 2 - Cloudy day

For the second scenario, the same initial conditions of the sunny day test are imposed on the cloudy day simulation. Figure 12 depicts the hierarchical control results when passing clouds disturb the solar thermal plant.

Here, important differences occur in the system’s configuration due to the low irradiance profile at the beginning and around 12 h. When the operation started, the solar collector field and the tanks’ temperatures were too low, which required switching on the gas heater. Then the irradiance increases, and the solar collectors and the tanks can power the absorption chiller. However, once again, the passing clouds reduce the irradiance, which

Figure 12: Hierarchical control results for the cloudy day scenario.

forces the systems to turn the gas heater on again. Notice that, differently from Scenario 1, $T_{g,in}(t)$ slightly extrapolates the reference some periods until the middle of the test. Nevertheless, a stable operation restarts at the end mainly because the subsystem's temperatures balance after starting the gas heater, and no more passing clouds disturb the solar plant.

Figure 13: PI-AW performance for the cloudy day scenario.

Accordingly, Fig. 13 portrays the lower layer control performance. Once again, the PI-AW controllers face no difficulties in achieving optimal references, even when the saturation limits situation occurs, demonstrating the well-designed effect of the AW component.

5.3. Performance analysis

Finally, quantitative performance indices are provided to analyze the proposed scenarios. Table 6 depicts the sum and the mean absolute error SAE and MAE (the error is considered when extrapolating the reference zone), the amount of time elapsed out the reference zone t_{err} , and the sum of control increments SCI concerning $u_{1_{opt}}(t)$, $u_{2_{opt}}(t)$ and $u_{3_{opt}}(t)$ (the indices are calculated for the operating time from 10 h to 15 h).

Table 6: Performance indices for the simulated scenarios

Indices	Sunny day	Cloudy day
SAE [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	6471.2	56887
MAE [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	0.36	3.16
t_{err} [min]	38	42
SIC_{u_1} [-]	118.90	321.77
SIC_{u_2} [-]	33.87	64.37
SIC_{u_3} [-]	99.63	358.17

From Table 6, it is possible to evidence the graphical results previously presented. First, Scenario 1 presents less error than Scenario 2, mainly due to cloud disturbances. Moreover, both scenarios demonstrate that the HP-NMPC tries to absorb the maximum thermal energy of the solar collectors, keeping $u_2(t)$ very steady at low flows while manipulating widely $u_1(t)$ and $u_3(t)$. Nevertheless, both scenarios demonstrate satisfactory performance and, mainly, respect the system operating conditions. It is worth mentioning that the proposed hierarchical controller produces a very smooth behavior of the controlled variables, demonstrating soft dynamics in modes switching due to the successful applied control concepts, such as dwell-time and stress zone, and well-designed operating conditions presented in Section 3. Therefore, the proposed hierarchical hybrid control strategy presents a promising solution for controlling an absorption chiller powered by a solar thermal facility.

6. Conclusions

This work presented a hierarchical controller based on a hybrid nonlinear predictive control strategy for a solar thermal facility focusing on powering an absorption chiller. Herein, the CIESOL facility is assumed as the objective of the investigation. First, the CIESOL absorption machine model is proposed, in which three models (first principles, ARX and NARX) are calibrated and validated with actual plant data. Then, a hierarchical control is formulated based on the HPNMPC for the upper layer and PI-AW for the lower layer.

As main conclusions, it can be highlighted that:

- although the proposed first principles model for the absorption chiller presented less than 1 °C of mean error in the validation results, further investigation must be done to replace the lumped parameters with descriptive thermodynamical terms to improve the representativeness of the models associating the different absorption chiller sections;
- the validated models and the proposed control framework can accurately represent the CIESOL plant, strengthening the simulated scenarios' faithfulness. Regarding the control strategy, important theoretical control aspects are implemented to improve the overall hybrid predictive control. By design, dwell-time and stress concepts are imposed in the operating conditions to reduce instability and chattering behavior concerning modes switching in the HPNMPC. Furthermore, PI-AW controllers are presented in the lower layer to reduce the nonlinear dynamic effects of control valves and minimize the effects of unmeasured disturbances in the manipulated variables, enhancing the robustness and performance of the overall control framework;
- the results demonstrated that the hierarchical controller can control the entire solar plant in a way that complies with the process criteria and achieves the desired inlet temperature of the absorber machine generator. This is a remarkable result since it provides more degrees of freedom for the control while guaranteeing the system operating conditions. Furthermore, the hierarchical controller presented an outstanding performance in sunny and cloudy simulated scenarios, which encourages the implementation of the proposed control framework in the existing system. As noted in Section 5, in only 14% of the simulated time, the water temperature was out of the reference zone, both

on sunny and cloudy days. This issue is characterized mainly by the tank's temperature as this subsystem requires enormous amounts of thermal energy to warm up promptly, which could not be physically achieved.

Finally, future works intend to extend the hierarchical structure by adding an upper optimization layer to regulate the operating conditions associated with specific process requirements, for instance, optimizing the tank storage, maximizing the solar collector thermal production, and minimizing the reference zone error for the absorption chiller. Furthermore, the presented control strategy is planned to be implemented in the existing system for practical results analysis, once the new supervisory control and data acquisition system is commissioned.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Igor M. L. Pataro: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - original draft, review and editing, Visualization. **Juan D. Gil:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - original draft, review and editing, Visualization. **José L. Guzmán:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - review, Visualization. **Manuel Berenguel:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - review, Visualization. **João M. Lemos:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - review, Visualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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